

Direct numerical simulations of turbulent pipe flow at high Reynolds numberA. Ceci * and S. Pirozzoli*Dipartimento di Ingegneria Meccanica e Aerospaziale, Sapienza Università di Roma,
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Flow in circular pipes is paradigmatic in the study of fluid turbulence. For compelling practical reasons, it was considered since pioneering studies dealing with hydraulic engineering [1], in which it continues to play a prominent role. Pipe flow was also the subject of the landmark study of Reynolds [2], which first highlighted the importance of what was later called the Reynolds number in determining the passage from a direct to a sinuous regime. Pipe flow was considered by Nikuradse [3] in the first systematic study of the effect of coarse and fine roughness on resistance as a function of the Reynolds number. Because of its theoretical and practical importance, pipe flow has been studied in modern experimental facilities, such as the Princeton Superpipe pressurized facility [4–6] and the CICLOPE facility of the University of Bologna [7,8], which however suffer from problems in accessing the near-wall layer. Direct numerical simulations (DNSs) are a better candidate than experiments to provide high-quality visualizations of turbulent flow. Direct numerical simulations of pipe flow have been numerous, although not as many as for channel flow, and include a number of notable works [9–13].

In a recent paper [14] the present authors first reported DNS results of pipe flow at friction Reynolds number from $Re_\tau \approx 180$ to $Re_\tau \approx 6000$ [here $Re_\tau = u_\tau R/\nu$, with $u_\tau = (\tau_w/\rho)^{1/2}$ the

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FIG. 1. Pipe geometry: (a) coordinate system and typical length scales and (b) location of reference shells used in the flow visualizations.

friction velocity, R the pipe radius, τ_w the wall shear stress, and ρ and ν the fluid density and kinematic viscosity]. Rendering and animations of the flow field computed from the DNS database of Pirozzoli *et al.* [14] have been generated by using the open-source cinematic package BLENDER [15] and the visualization toolkit PARAVIEW [16]. Full automation of the process of animation generation has been achieved by means of the PVPYTHON backend. The numerical simulations are carried out in a domain with axial length $15R$ [see Fig. 1(a)]. In the figure we also show for reference two cylindrical shells corresponding to a near-wall position $y^+ \approx 15$ ($y = R - r$ is the distance from the wall and the plus superscript denotes normalization with wall units u_τ and ν) and farther from it, namely, $y/R = 0.3$.

The instantaneous axial velocity field at $\text{Re}_\tau = 6000$ is shown in Fig. 2. The flow in the cross-stream plane [Fig. 2(a)] features a limited number of bulges distributed along the azimuthal direction, which correspond to alternating intrusions of high-speed fluid from the pipe core and ejections of low-speed fluid from the wall. As in all canonical wall-bounded flow, flow-aligned streaks are visible in the near-wall cylindrical shell [17]. The organization of the streaks is clearly on two different length scales: On top of a sea of tiny streaks, larger zones with velocity higher than the mean (in red) and lower than the mean (in blue) are visible, which are elongated along the axial direction and whose size is comparable to the pipe radius.

Additional information about the large-scale streaks, which are referred to as very-large-scale motions [18], is provided in Fig. 3, where we show axial velocity contours in the two reference cylindrical shells, after unrolling for ease of interpretation. Scale separation between small- and

FIG. 2. DNS of pipe flow at $\text{Re}_\tau = 6000$: instantaneous axial velocity field (a) in a cross-stream plane and (b) at $y^+ \approx 15$. The color scale ranges from 0 (blue) to $1.3u_b$ (red) and the white isoline in (a) marks the isolevel $u_z/u_b = 0.9$.

FIG. 3. DNS of pipe flow at $Re_\tau = 6000$: instantaneous axial velocity field u_z/u_b , in unrolled cylindrical shells, at (a) $y^+ = 15$ and (b) $y/R = 0.3$. The color scale ranges from 0 (blue) to $1.3u_b$ (red).

large-scale streaks is here more clearly visible, with large structures scaling with R and small ones scaling in wall units. Hand-sketched black lines are used to trace the approximate boundaries of the large-scale high- and low-speed streaks in the near-wall shell, which are also reported in the $y/R = 0.3$ shell [Fig. 3(b)]. Remarkable association is observed, which proves with little doubt that large-scale near-wall organization results from imprinting of large eddies residing in the core part of the flow [19].

Reynolds number effects are emphasized in Fig. 4, in which we compare DNSs at extreme Reynolds numbers. Figure 4(a) strikingly highlights that, despite the presence of finer details, the flow organization at the large scales at $Re_\tau = 6000$ is very similar to the case $Re_\tau = 180$, both in the near-wall shell and in the core flow. This is corroborated by Fig. 4(b), which shows that the large-scale organization of the velocity field is essentially unaffected by a large change of the Reynolds number. In fact, analysis of the azimuthal spectra shows the dominance of the $k_\theta = 4$ mode in both cases.

In summary, the flow visualizations reported herein provide strong support for the idea that turbulence in pipe flow results from superposition and interaction of near-wall dynamics occurring on viscous length scales and timescales and of a core flow dynamics whose typical eddies scale on R and which just like the former is characterized by streamwise leaning streaks which are meandering in the azimuthal directions. This evidence seems to be in support of the scenario envisaged by Dennis and Sogaro [20], based on experimental measurements at lower Reynolds number.

A baseline software supporting the findings of this paper can be found in [21]. The code can also be found in [22].

FIG. 4. Comparison of axial velocity fields for DNS at $Re_\tau = 180$ and 6000: (a) near-wall shell (left) and $y/R = 0.3$ shell (right) and (b) cross-stream plane.

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